

Audit of Diagnosis, Monitoring, and Management of Gestational Hypertension According to NICE NG133

Audit Question

To what extent does current practice in our OBGYN department comply with NICE NG133 recommendations for the management of gestational hypertension?

Background

Gestational hypertension is defined as new-onset hypertension ($\geq 140/90$ mmHg) after 20 weeks of gestation without significant proteinuria. It is associated with increased risks of maternal and fetal complications if not properly monitored and treated.

The NICE guideline NG133 outlines clear standards regarding diagnosis, monitoring, fetal surveillance, and antihypertensive management.

This audit aims to assess the compliance of the obstetrics and gynecology department with the recommended standards for the diagnosis and management of gestational hypertension.

Aim

To evaluate the level of compliance with NICE NG133 recommendations regarding the diagnosis, monitoring, and management of gestational hypertension in pregnant women attending the obstetrics and gynecology department. This audit follows a

complete audit cycle including baseline assessment, implementation of an improvement plan, and re-audit.

Audit Standards (Gestational Hypertension per NICE NG133):

Diagnosis Standard:

Women must meet criteria for gestational hypertension (BP \geq 140/90 after 20 weeks, no proteinuria).

Blood Pressure Monitoring:

- BP should be checked once or twice weekly.

Proteinuria Testing:

- Dipstick testing once or twice weekly.

Laboratory Monitoring:

- Full blood count, renal and liver function tests at diagnosis and then weekly.

Fetal Monitoring:

- Ultrasound growth scan at diagnosis, then every 2–4 weeks if normal.

Antihypertensive Management:

- Offer treatment if BP remains $>$ 140/90 mmHg.
- Target BP = \leq 135/85 mmHg.
- Labetalol first line.

Admission Criteria:

- Severe hypertension $\geq 160/110$ must be admitted.

Timing of Birth:

- Do NOT offer planned birth before 37 weeks unless indicated.

Factor	Hypertension: BP 140/90 to 159/109 mmHg	Severe hypertension: BP of 160/110 mmHg or more
Admission to hospital	Do not routinely admit to hospital	Admit, but if BP falls below 160/110 mmHg then manage as for hypertension
Antihypertensive pharmacological treatment	Offer pharmacological treatment if BP remains over 140/90 mmHg	Offer pharmacological treatment to all women
Target BP on antihypertensive treatment	Aim for BP of 135/85 mmHg or less	Aim for BP of 135/85 mmHg or less
BP measurement	Once or twice a week (depending on BP) until BP is 135/85 mmHg or less	Every 15 to 30 minutes until BP is less than 160/110 mmHg
Dipstick proteinuria testing	Once or twice a week (with BP measurement)	Daily while admitted
Blood tests	Measure full blood count, liver function and renal function at presentation and then weekly	Measure full blood count, liver function and renal function at presentation and then weekly
Placental growth factor (PIGF)-based testing	Carry out PIGF-based testing on 1 occasion (NICE diagnostic guidance DG49) if there is suspicion of preeclampsia	Carry out PIGF-based testing on 1 occasion (NICE diagnostic guidance DG49) if there is suspicion of preeclampsia
Fetal heart auscultation	Offer fetal heart auscultation at every antenatal appointment	Offer fetal heart auscultation at every antenatal appointment
Fetal ultrasound	Carry out ultrasound assessment of the fetus at diagnosis and, if normal, repeat every 2 to 4 weeks, if clinically indicated	Carry out ultrasound assessment of the fetus at diagnosis and, if normal, repeat every 2 weeks, if severe hypertension persists
Cardiotocography (CTG)	Carry out a CTG only if clinically indicated	Carry out a CTG at diagnosis and then only if clinically indicated

Study Design

This is a retrospective clinical audit comparing current clinical practice in the management of gestational hypertension against the NICE NG133 standards.

Setting

Obstetrics and Gynecology Department, Tanta University Hospitals.

Study Population

Pregnant women diagnosed with gestational hypertension (BP \geq 140/90 mmHg after 20 weeks without proteinuria) attending the antenatal clinic or admitted to the obstetrics ward during the study period.

Inclusion Criteria

- Pregnant women \geq 20 weeks gestation.
- Diagnosis of gestational hypertension (mild or severe).
- Complete records including BP readings, investigations, and fetal assessments.

Exclusion Criteria

- Chronic hypertension (diagnosed before 20 weeks).
- Pre-eclampsia cases (hypertension + proteinuria or organ dysfunction).
- Incomplete medical records.

Sample Size

A minimum of 60-80 cases will be included, depending on availability.

This follows common audit practice standards to ensure representativeness and feasibility.

Data Collection Method

1. Identify eligible cases

- Review the antenatal clinic logbook and electronic patient register
- Review ward admission books for obstetric patients diagnosed with gestational or severe hypertension

2. Retrieve patient records

- Outpatient clinic paper files
- Inpatient records and observation charts
- BP charts, drug charts, and nursing notes
- Ultrasound reports
- Laboratory investigation reports

3. Extract anonymized data

Using a structured data collection sheet, the following will be collected:

- Demographics
- BP readings
- Proteinuria results
- Labs
- Antihypertensive treatment
- Fetal monitoring
- Admission indications
- Timing of birth

4. Anonymization

- All data will be coded
- No names, MRNs, phone numbers, or identifiers will be collected

5. Data entry

- Data will be entered into an Excel sheet for analysis
- Each case will be evaluated against NICE NG133 criteria

Data Analysis

Each case will be assessed against each NICE standard and classified as:

- Compliant
- Non-compliant
- Not applicable

Compliance (%) =

$(\text{Number of compliant cases} \div \text{total eligible cases}) \times 100$

Results will be presented in:

- Tables
- Bar charts / pie charts
- Summary commentary

Ethical Considerations

This project is registered as a Clinical Audit and does not require Research Ethics Committee approval; therefore:

- No patient consent is required
- All data are anonymized
- Audit is conducted under hospital clinical governance policies

Approval was obtained formally from the Head of Department, Executive Manger of Tanta University Hospitals and Head of Quality Assurance Unit.

Audit Cycle

- Data collection: 2–3 weeks
- Analysis: 1 week
- Presentation & Action Plan: 1 week
- Re-audit: After 6–8 weeks